

Supplementary file to the paper
**„Cognitive-affective trust towards international e-commerce
platforms: the study of Polish young consumers”**

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Survey questionnaire

Demographics

1. What is your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary person
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

2. What is your age?

- 18–24
- 25–34
- 35–44
- 45–54
- 55+

3. Please select your highest achieved level of education:

According to ISCED-2011 classification recommended by OECD:

Below secondary = ISCED 0–2: primary, lower secondary, basic vocational schools;

Secondary = ISCED 3–4: general upper secondary, technical, post-secondary non-tertiary;

Higher = ISCED 5–8: bachelor's, engineer's, master's and above.

- Below secondary
- Secondary
- Higher

4. What is your place of residence?

- Village/rural
- Town up to 50,000 inhabitants
- City up to 200,000 inhabitants
- City over 200,000 inhabitants

5. How many people reside in your household, including yourself?

Household (according to Statistics Poland): a group of people living together and sharing expenses. Single persons maintaining themselves form one-person households.

- 1
- 2

- 3
- 4
- 5
- More than 5

6. Which of the following best describes the financial situation of your household?

- We have enough money for everything, without making any sacrifices
- We have enough money for almost everything, but we have to set aside money for more expensive, major purchases
- We have enough money for basic expenses (such as food, clothing and apartment fees), but we are unable to afford more expensive, more serious purchases
- We barely have enough money for basic expenses (like food, clothing and housing fees) and have to forgo some expenses
- We don't have enough money at all even for basic expenses (like food, clothing and housing fees)
- Prefer not to say

7. In the past year, have you made at least one purchase through an online sales platform?

Online sales platform – a service where many selling companies offer their products in one place, e.g., Allegro, Amazon, Empik.com, Temu

- Yes
- No

General Issues Concerning Online Shopping

8. Using which device do you most often make online purchases?

I make online purchases...

- Exclusively using a desktop computer or laptop
- More often using a desktop computer or laptop
- Equally often using both a desktop computer/laptop and a smartphone/tablet
- More often using a smartphone or tablet
- Exclusively using a smartphone or tablet

9. In the past year, have you made at least one purchase through an international online sales platform (e.g., Temu, Zalando, AliExpress, Amazon)?

- Yes
- No

General Issues Concerning International Online Sales Platforms

10. I more often shop on online sales platforms which are...

Originating from Poland											International
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

11. On which international online sales platforms did you most often make purchases during the last year? Select up to 3 options:

- Amazon
- Temu
- eBay
- Zalando
- AliExpress
- Shopee
- Etsy
- Alibaba
- John Lewis
- Other: _____

12. How often do you make purchases on international online sales platforms?

- Daily or almost daily
- Several times a week
- Several times a month
- Several times a year
- About once a year

13. Which product categories did you buy most often on international online platforms in the past year? Select up to 4 options:

- Books (including e-books)
- Video games
- Music and films
- Electronics
- Office supplies
- Home and garden
- Children and toys
- Food products
- Beauty and health
- Household (including cleaning products)
- Fashion (clothing, footwear and accessories)
- Sports and tourism
- Pets
- Hobbies (other than music and film)
- Automotive
- Collectibles and art

Trust while online shopping

14. Below you will find several general statements about trust on the internet. Please indicate to what extent you agree with them (scale: 0 = “strongly disagree”, 10 = “strongly agree”).

- a) I have a positive attitude toward online shopping.
- b) Most online shops are trustworthy.
- c) Most sellers on online sales platforms (e.g. Allegro, Amazon, Zalando, Temu) are trustworthy.

- d) I believe that the law effectively protects my personal data when shopping online.
- e) Online payments (via BLIK, PayU, PayPal, etc.) are trustworthy.

Factors influencing trust in online sales platforms (part 1)

15. Which of the following factors genuinely increase your trust in a given online sales platform? Rate each from 0 to 10, where 0 = “does not increase my trust at all” and 10 = “completely increases my trust.”

- a) The online sales platform uses visible security certificates (e.g., the “green padlock” in the browser address bar).
- b) The online sales platform clearly informs about its privacy policy and the use of personal data.
- c) The content presented on the online sales platform’s website is clear and understandable.
- d) The prices offered by the online sales platform are displayed clearly and understandably.
- e) The online sales platform’s website is easy to navigate.
- f) Personal trust in the country of origin of the online sales platform on which I make purchases.
- g) Previous positive experiences with the online sales platform.

Factors influencing trust in online sales platforms (part 2)

16. Which of the following factors genuinely increase your trust in a given online sales platform? Rate each from 0 to 10, where 0 = “does not increase my trust at all” and 10 = “completely increases my trust.”

- a) The online sales platform’s website has a pleasant, attractive, or aesthetic design/appearance.
- b) Products on the online shopping service are presented through attractive image galleries.
- c) The way the online sales platform advertises itself evokes positive emotions in me.
- d) The prices offered by the online sales platform are attractive to me.
- e) The online sales platform supports user interaction through social features such as live chat and live reviews.
- f) The online sales platform contains engaging interactive features (e.g. augmented reality, lotteries).
- g) I notice the online sales platform’s involvement in activities benefiting people, society or the environment.
- h) I have favourable opinions about the online sales platform from other users, including family or friends.

Perceived quality of the e-commerce market

17. Generally, when I buy something online, I tend to trust online sales platforms...

Originating from Poland more											International ones more
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

18. Below are selected factors affecting the quality of online shopping. Please indicate on a scale of 0–10 which platforms you trust more in each aspect (0 = Polish platforms, 10 = international platforms):

- a) Technical reliability of the platform (e.g., no errors on the website)
- b) Professional customer service
- c) Efficiency of returns or complaints
- d) Convenient delivery conditions
- e) Payment security
- f) Accuracy of product descriptions and photos
- g) Price transparency (e.g., no hidden charges)
- h) Overall feeling of shopping safety

Failure to engage with international online sales platforms

19. How do you rate your trust in international online sales platforms?

I do not trust them at all											I fully trust them
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

20. For what reasons do you not shop on international online sales platforms?

Select up to 4, in your opinion the most important reasons:

- I prefer Polish platforms
- I do not have such a need to use them
- I am afraid the product will not be delivered on time or at all
- Expensive delivery options
- I am afraid the shipment will arrive damaged
- Platforms do not offer enough payment options
- I am afraid of leakage of my personal data
- I encounter problems with the functioning of the platform
- I do not like to support international corporations
- I do not know a foreign language
- Lack of product availability
- Lack of or poorly functioning mobile application
- Product descriptions/photos do not reflect the real state of affairs
- I believe such platforms do not comply with safety standards
- I have ethical concerns about the activities of such platforms
- Other: _____

21. Which of the following factors would realistically increase your trust in international online sales platforms? Rate each from 0 to 10, where 0 = “would not increase my trust at all” and 10 = “would completely increase my trust.”

- a) Greater number of positive reviews and ratings from other customers.
- b) The possibility of easy product returns.
- c) Accurate and clear product/service descriptions with high-quality photos.

- d) The possibility of purchasing products/services from verified or official sellers.
- e) Presence of security certificates by the online shopping service (e.g., “green padlock” in the browser address bar).
- f) Provision of varied delivery options.
- g) Guaranteed/on-time delivery of ordered products on the next working day.
- h) Customer support that is efficient and easily accessible.
- i) The possibility to view a product live (e.g., via streaming video).
- j) Greater transparency in privacy policy and personal data protection.
- k) Presence of a mobile application for the online shopping service.
- l) Increased website/app interactivity (e.g., live chat, virtual advisors).
- m) Greater involvement of the online shopping service in environmental or social activities.
- n) Participation of famous people (including influencers) in promoting the online shopping service.
- o) Reliable and engaging marketing campaigns of the online shopping service (e.g., ads, banners, promotions).
- p) Greater ease of use of online shopping services.
- r) More transparent information about the country of origin of the online shopping service.